

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE TYMUS OF 33-38 WEEKS ANTENATALLY DEATH INFANTS

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Abstract: Those who died from intrauterine infection in the antenatal period make up 78.2% of all babies and form the basis of our research. Lagging behind the morphological development in the thyroid gland: it is characterized by the fact that the cortex of the thymus covers a very small area of the medulla, and there are almost no lymphocytes. As the main morphological substrate of these changes, the reticuloepithelial cells of the thymus cortical layer are small in size, the desmosomas are short and thick, the sparse fibrous structures connecting the desmosomas are abundant in the perivascular areas of the cortical layer, and the hematohistogenic barrier is brought to a functionally impaired state.

Key words: thymus, morphology, involution, immunodeficiency, necrosis, apoptosis.

The urgency of the problem. In terms of newborns in the world, the average is 4-5 per 1000 births in the USA and Europe. In the world's top five, Turkmenistan has 45, Tajikistan 33, Azerbaijan 21, Kyrgyzstan 17 and Uzbekistan 16 cases per 1000 births. This indicates that full screening of extragenital diseases during fetal development or examinations that should be done during pregnancy have not been fully implemented. In perinatal pathologies, antenatal death mainly develops together with infectious and non-infectious etiological processes and manifests itself in the form of fetal immaturity, asphyxia, birth trauma, pneumopathies, perinatal blood circulation disorders in the brain, and hemorrhagic disease of newborns.

The purpose of the research is to study the pathomorphological characteristics of the thymus tissue during antenatal death of infants.

Materials and methods : Morphological methods of thymus tissue of stillborn babies were used in the antenatal period.

Discussion and result : In this group, mainly, the thymus of infants whose mothers were infected, confirmed in the autopsy materials to be affected by intra-fetal infection, were taken for study. The average weight of the thymus of babies in this group is 7.21 ± 1.31 grams, and the thymus of healthy babies of the same period is 9.85 ± 2.17 grams. The average thymus weight was found to be 28.65% smaller than the norm (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Antenatal death of a baby born at 36 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. In the medullary layer, the denuded foci of the stroma are identified. Fullness is determined in blood vessels of all layers. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

Since the purpose of our study was to study the morphological aspects of the thymus of babies who died antenatally, the specificity of the morphological changes that occurred in the thymus of stillborn fetuses was studied, taking into account that those who died from various pathologies (infectious factors) were .

At 33-36 weeks of intrauterine development of the fetus, the effect of secondary infections developed in the mother on the development of the thymus was not strongly manifested. The main changes were secondary changes in the morphofunctional areas of the salivary gland, the formation of a large number of Gassal bodies, and the signs of fullness in the veins were determined (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Antenatal death of a baby born at 38 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. In the medullary layer, the denuded foci of the stroma are identified. Fullness is determined in blood vessels of all layers. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

Let us remind you that antenatal infant death is mainly observed in the preterm delivery periods, and as the term approaches, it is characterized by the relative development of the primary and secondary immune organs in infants, the development of germinal centers in the follicles of the immune organs: lymph nodes, spleen, MALT structures under the influence of infectious factors from the outside, already during fetal development. , these signs in the thymus, the cells are the marrow It is characterized by the distribution of large-sized lymphocytes migrating through the postcapillary venules in the layer, the ratio of the cortex layer and the medulla layer being almost the same, the accumulation of a large number of small-sized lymphocytes around the walls of reticuloepithelial cells, and the clear appearance of differentiation areas in the corticomedullary area (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Antenatal death of a baby born at 37 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. In the medullary layer, the denuded foci of the stroma are identified. Fullness is determined in blood vessels of all layers. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

In our study, 33-36-week-old babies who died from various infectious factors and were stillborn were taken. According to the organometric parameters of the thymus according to the gestational period, morphologically the following were determined. It was found that the external fibrous capsule has grown into the cortex in a trabecular form, the septal barriers are sharply expanded, and there are many rough structures with fibroblasts and collagen fibers. At the same time, the fullness of trabecular blood vessels, the development of interstitial tumors formed in the perivascular area, and in many cases, the presence of foci of disorganization in the fibrous structures were determined (see Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Antenatal death of a baby born at 38 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. In the medullary layer, the denuded foci of the stroma are identified. Fullness is determined in blood vessels of all layers. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

of dark hyperchromic nuclei with foci of small-sized lymphocytes in the cortex . A large accumulation of macrophages in the cortex, fragments of apoptized lymphocytes in the cytoplasm are detected. Reticulo-epithelial cells are located along the perimeter of the lobes, and small lymphocyte foci clusters are identified around their walls. In the interval, foci of reticulocytes and sparse fibers located in different directions were identified, which formed the basis of the swollen thymic stroma, and nurse cells were located along the perimeter of the cortical layer, and a small number of small lymphocytes were found around it (see Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Antenatally dead baby born at 33 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. In the medullary layer, the denuded foci of the stroma are identified. Fullness is determined in blood vessels of all layers. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

These morphological manifestations confirm that the thymus is morphofunctionally underactive. A large number of foci of lymphocyte collection that underwent induced apoptosis was also similar to the thymus tissue of small gestational age, the ratio of cortex and medulla was 1/5, and the average thickness was $151.25 \pm 5.16 \mu\text{m}$, compared to the control group. , was found to be $121.16 \pm 3.12 \mu\text{m}$. This means that the statistical aspects differ by an average of 20.6%. It is characterized by the thickness of the cortical layers, and the medullary layer, which is composed of light-colored cells and occupies an average area of $51.15 \pm 1.16 \mu\text{m}$, which is 2.7 times less than the control group (see Figure 6). .

Figure 6. Antenatally dead baby born at 33 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

According to the main morphological substrata of the thymus of stillborn babies in the period of 33-36 weeks, it was manifested by the presence of Gassal corpuscles in the cortical layer, fullness in venous blood vessels, detection of petrified small foci, distribution of light cytoplasmic lymphocytes in the stroma (see Figs. 7-8).

Figure 7. Antenatally dead baby born at 33 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. In the medullary layer, the denuded lesions of the stroma are identified. Fullness is determined in blood vessels of all layers. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

Figure 8. Antenatally dead baby born at 33 weeks of age. Minutes 49D. In the structure of the thymus lobe, Gassal's corpuscles (1) of different sizes, which develop without selecting a boundary, the growth of the trabecular barrier in the cortical layer to the medullary layer, and the swellings formed in the interval are determined. In the medullary layer, the denuded foci of the stroma are identified. Fullness is determined in blood vessels of all layers. Paint G.E. The size is 10x10.

In the medullary layer, cells with high cytoplasm of postcapillary venules have turned into normal endotheliocytes, tumors have formed between them, small-caliber vein blood vessels have remained full, dystrophic changes in reticuloepithelial cells, mainly horn dystrophy, and a large number of Gassal corpuscles have improved. It was found that formed lymphocytes were found in small numbers, macrophages with large pale cytoplasm, and reticulocytes were increased. These identified signs mean that the thymus has undergone accidental transformation from a clinical and morphological point of view, and it confirms the occurrence of primary cellular immunodeficiency due to the development of intrauterine infection in stillborn babies at 33-36 weeks. Precisely, at 33-36 weeks, the size of the thymus is reduced by 28.6% compared to the control group, which is also explained by the fact that it developed in parallel with the enlargement of the adrenal gland. Because the integral relationship between the thymus and the adrenal gland means that the damage factors are focused on the primary immune organs, which leads to the enlargement of the adrenal gland.

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